

A CRITERION FOR THE ONSET OF SURFACE INSTABILITIES OF ORTHOTROPIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

We present a criterion for estimating the onset of surface instabilities in reinforced solids subjected to uniaxial compression. This involves a combination of two buckling modes: a macroscopic mode in which we treat the composite as a homogeneous orthotropic solid pre-compressed along the stiffest direction, and a microscopic mode in which we consider the buckling of a single layer of the reinforcement bonded to a substrate of the matrix material. Both criteria, which are based on mathematically rigorous results, are presented in a simple form allowing the computation of the critical buckling load in a straightforward and simple manner.

INTRODUCTION

The problem of estimating the compressive strength of reinforced composites is important since these anisotropic materials have become common in modern engineering applications. Among the various relevant works we cite that of Biot [1] who developed a method for dealing with the initiation of surface instabilities. With the growing usage of composite materials Rosen [2], who introduced the concept of bifurcation at the micro level, obtained the well-known estimate that the compressive strength is equal to the effective inplane shear modulus of the composite. This estimate has been rederived by different methods and has also been the basis for more sophisticated models involving initial imperfections of the composites. Extensive experimental and numerical study of the subject, including references to earlier works, can be found in [3].

In this work, we propose a new criterion for estimating the onset of surface instabilities of reinforced composites. We assume that the composite is linearly elastic and that there are two dominant buckling modes, a macro-buckling mode and a micro-buckling mode. The criterion for the macro-buckling is developed from a rigorous result obtained in [4] for analyzing the bifurcation of pre-stressed orthotropic solids. The micro-buckling criterion is based on recent work by Shield *et al.* [5], dealing with the buckling of a thin layer bonded to an infinite substrate. In the application section, we apply the proposed criterion to a specific laminated composite and find that for common volume fractions of the reinforcement constituent (40 to 50%) the macroscopic criterion is lower than the microscopic one, while for dilute concentrations the microscopic mode is the dominant one. We also find that the new criterion is tighter than the buckling criterion proposed in [2] and conforms with corresponding extensive analysis carried out by Geymonat *et al.* [6].

ANALYSIS

We consider a composite specimen of overall orthotropic symmetry which is subjected to uniaxial compression along the stiffest direction, *e.g.*, along the fibers or the layers. For simplicity, throughout the following analysis we assume a *plane strain* condition, and thus, both classes of fiber-reinforced and laminated composites will be idealized as two-dimensional laminates. We also restrict the discussion to *linearly elastic* composites, neglecting effects that may rise due to material nonlinearity. As mentioned in the introduction, we consider two buckling modes, a macroscopic mode in which we treat the composite as a homogeneous medium, and a microscopic mode in which we consider a single layer of the reinforcement material bonded to an infinite substrate of the matrix material. The macroscopic and microscopic analyses are based, respectively, on the works of deBotton and Schulgasser [4] and Shield *et al.* [5]. Both results are obtained by application of a large deformation approach and in the remainder of this section we provide a short summary highlighting some relevant aspects of these two works.

MACROSCOPIC BUCKLING

The macroscopic buckling criterion is obtained by considering a halfspace ($x_2 \leq 0$) of the composite. We assume that the composite is pre-compressed along the x_1 -direction, which is aligned with the fibers or the layers. Following [4], in terms of the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress the equilibrium equations are

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{11,1} + \sigma_{12,2} - p u_{1,1} &= 0, \\ \sigma_{12,1} + \sigma_{22,2} - p u_{2,1} &= 0,\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where σ_{ij} are the components of a small stress increment from the initially pre-stressed condition, p is the initial compression along the x_1 -direction, and u_i are the components of the displacement field (comma denotes spatial derivatives with respect to the pertinent coordinate). From the assumption of linearly elastic constitutive behavior it follows that

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u_{1,1} \\ u_{2,2} \\ u_{1,1} + u_{2,2} \end{pmatrix}\tag{2}$$

where C_{11} , C_{22} , C_{12} and C_{66} are the components of the *effective* stiffness matrix. By making use of Eqn. (2) in the equilibrium equations (1), a set of two partial differential equations for u_1 and u_2 is obtained. A relatively simple solution can be found for these two equations [4], and by utilizing Eqn. (2) once again, an *explicit* form for the stress components can be determined. These stress components must satisfy the boundary conditions $\sigma_{12} = 0$ and $\sigma_{22} = 0$ at the free boundary $x_2 = 0$. It was shown [4] that when the ratio of the Young's modulus along the x_1 -direction to the Young's modulus along the x_2 -direction is large, the condition for the existence of a nonhomogeneous solution may be expressed in the form

$$C_{22}(C_{66} - p)(E - p)^2 - C_{66}(C_{11} - p)p^2 = 0,\tag{3}$$

where $E \equiv (C_{11}C_{22} - C_{12}^2)/C_{22}$ is the *plane strain* Young's modulus along the x_1 -direction. The cubic equation (3) provides a condition for the onset of a surface instability, and we refer to the smallest positive root of Eqn. (3) as the macroscopic critical stress p_{cr}^0 .

Figure 1. The spatial arrangement of the reinforcing layer. (a) The configuration considered by Shield *et al.* [5]. (b) A realistic configuration. (c) An alternative view of configuration (b) as involving a "composite" layer bonded to a substrate in the form of configuration (a).

MICROSCOPIC BUCKLING

The criterion for the microscopic buckling is obtained by following the procedure developed by Shield *et al.* [5] for determining the critical compressive strain of a thin isotropic layer bonded to the upper surface of an infinite isotropic halfspace. It is assumed that the medium is pre-compressed along the x_1 -direction, which is aligned with the layer, and that, initially, the interface between the layer and the substrate is the plane $x_2 = 0$. Although originally presented in a slightly different form, this problem can be solved by considering, in each of the two constituents separately, the equilibrium and constitutive equations (1) and (2), respectively. A general form for the displacement and stress fields can be found [5] in a manner reminiscent of the one described in the previous section.

In a nonhomogeneous state of deformation, the displacement of the interface may be expressed in the form [5]

$$\begin{aligned} u_1 &= U_1 \sin \omega x_1, \\ u_2 &= U_2 \cos \omega x_1, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where ω is the frequency of the waviness of the layer after deformation and U_1 and U_2 are arbitrary constants. The four traction and displacement continuity conditions that must be satisfied at the interface enable one to express the stress fields in the layer and the substrate in terms of U_1 and U_2 only. Then, the zero traction boundary conditions at the upper surface of the layer provide a set of two homogeneous equations for these two constants. The condition for the existence of a nontrivial solution for these equations, which is also the condition for the onset of an instability due to buckling of the layer, is that the determinant of the coefficients of U_1 and U_2 vanishes. This, in turn, provides the desired condition for the critical frequency ω_{cr} and the microscopic critical strain ϵ_{cr}^i . The corresponding estimate for the microscopic critical stress is

$$p_{cr}^i = E \epsilon_{cr}^i. \quad (5)$$

We note that in the above configuration the reinforcing layer is bonded to the outer surface of the matrix (Fig. 1a), a configuration which is probably not very adequate for composite materials. A more suitable configuration is the one presented in Fig. 1b, in which an additional layer of the matrix material is bonded on top of the reinforcing layer. A complete analysis of this, more involved configuration, is of course more difficult. However, we emphasize that the critical buckling strain primarily depends on the contrast between the longitudinal Young's moduli of the substrate and the layer, in such a way that the larger the contrast is the lower the critical strain becomes [5]. Further, the agreement between the beam theory approximation for

Figure 2. The microscopic buckling strain plotted as a function of the Poisson's ratio of the substrate for three values of the Poisson's ratio of the layer ν_L and three values of the stiffness ratio K (5, 20, and 50). The continuous curves correspond to $\nu_L = 0.45$, the dotted curves to $\nu_L = 0.25$, and the long-dashed curves to $\nu_L = 0.05$.

ϵ_{cr}^i and the exact results of Shield *et al.* [5], as well as the low sensitivity of ϵ_{cr}^i to the Poisson's ratio of the layer material (see the Application section below) suggests that the contributions of the other elastic properties of the layer to the critical strain are small. Accordingly, it is reasonable to expect that the differences between the buckling strain of an isotropic layer and an anisotropic one, both bonded on top of similar isotropic substrates and both having the same longitudinal plane strain Young's modulus, will be relatively small. In view of these observations, it is expected that the critical buckling strain of a "composite" layer made up of a matrix material layer, reinforcing material layer and again a matrix material layer, all bonded to an infinite substrate of the matrix material (Fig. 1c) will be higher than the buckling strain of the simple configuration considered above. This expectation is on grounds of the relatively low contrast between the longitudinal Young's moduli of the "composite" layer and the substrate in comparison with the high contrast between the Young's moduli of the reinforcement and the matrix. In this aspect, the microscopic buckling criterion proposed in this work is probably a *conservative* one.

Additionally, we note that this criterion for the microscopic buckling stress implicitly implies that the distance to the next neighboring layer inside the substrate is very large, an assumption which is suitable only in the dilute case. On the other hand, we note that by taking into account the contribution of the other layers in the substrate we will decrease the contrast between the longitudinal Young's moduli of the layer and the substrate. (Since the effective Young's modulus of the composite is larger than that of the matrix.) Accordingly, the predictions for the critical buckling strains and stresses will be higher. We may conclude then that this implicit assumption of maximum contrast between the properties of the layer and substrate possibly makes this microscopic buckling criterion even stricter.

Figure 3. The microscopic buckling strain plotted versus the stiffness ratio K for three values of the Poisson's ratio of the substrate ($\nu_s = 0.25, 0.35, 0.45$).

APPLICATION

We apply the results discussed in the previous section to obtain predictions for the critical buckling stress of reinforced composites. We note that the macroscopic criterion can easily be determined by solving the cubic equation (3) which is expressed in terms of the effective elastic properties of the composite. These properties can be found either by direct experimental measurements or by applications of various homogenization techniques involving the properties of the constituents and their spatial arrangement. The situation is more complicated as regards the computation of the microscopic buckling criterion, and numerical programming is required to obtain a solution for the problem. However, we note that due to the asymptotic nature of the problem, the critical buckling strain ϵ_{cr}^i depends only on the properties of the two constituents, and not on their arrangement within the composite. Further, we also note that the dependence of ϵ_{cr}^i on the Poisson's ratio of the layer material is weak. This is demonstrated in Fig. 2 that shows the microscopic buckling strain as a function of ν_s , the Poisson's ratio of the substrate, for three values of the Poisson's ratio of the layer ($\nu_L = 0.05, 0.25, 0.45$) and three ratios between the plane strain Young's modulus of the layer and that of the matrix ($K = 5, 20, 50$), where

$$K \equiv \frac{E_L}{(1-\nu_L^2)} \frac{(1-\nu_s^2)}{E_s}, \quad (6)$$

and where E_L and E_s are the Young's moduli of the layer and the substrate, respectively. We observe that in the limit of large contrast between the Young's moduli the influence of the Poisson's ratio of the layer is negligible, and even when the contrast is small ($K \approx 5$) the variations of the buckling strain due to changes in ν_L are approximately 5%. We may conclude then, that the microscopic buckling strain depends, primarily, on the stiffness ratio K and the Poisson's ratio of the matrix, and can be calculated once and for all regardless of other parameters characterizing the composite. Representative values for the critical strain as a function of the stiffness ratio for three common values of ν_s are given in Table 1. The

Figure 4. Estimates for the critical compressive stress of a laminated E-glass/epoxy composite normalized by the in-plane shear moduli G_{12} plotted versus the volume fraction of the E-glass. The continuous curve corresponds to the buckling criterion proposed in the present work and the long-dash curve to the beam theory based criterion of Rosen [2].

dependence of ϵ_{cr}^i on these two parameters is also shown in Fig 3. For the sake of completeness, we mention that in Table 1 and Fig. 3 the Poisson's ratio of the layer is $\nu_L = 0.2$. Results for higher values of K can be determined by application of the explicit beam theory based approximation given in [5]. (Note that the first term of Eqn. (17) in [5] should read $\Omega_c^2/12$ rather than $\Omega_c/12$ as appears there.)

Table 1. Numerical estimates for the microscopic buckling strain ϵ_{cr}^i as a function of the stiffness ratio K and ν_s , the Poisson's ratio of the substrate.

	$K = 2.5$	5	10	15	20	25	35	50
$\nu_s = 0.25$	0.241	0.174	0.118	0.0925	0.0773	0.0671	0.0541	0.0428
0.35	0.219	0.159	0.108	0.0851	0.0714	0.0621	0.0501	0.0399
0.45	0.195	0.142	0.0981	0.0779	0.0653	0.0571	0.0463	0.0371

By way of example, we apply the proposed buckling criterion to a laminar E-glass-reinforced epoxy composite. The Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio of the epoxy matrix are, respectively, $E_{ep} = 3.5$ GPa and $\nu_{ep} = 0.35$, and the corresponding values for the E-glass are $E_{gl} = 72$ GPa and $\nu_{gl} = 0.2$. Exact values for the effective elastic properties of the composite, in terms of the volume fraction of the reinforcing layers, are easily determined (see, for example, [7]). The macroscopic buckling stress is then computed by applying of Eqn. 3. The stiffness ratio for these two constituents is $K = 18.8$, the corresponding microscopic buckling strain is $\epsilon_{cr}^i = 0.0741$ (this value may be interpolated from Table 1), and the buckling stress is obtained by making use of Eqn. 5. Results for the joint macroscopic-microscopic criterion are plotted in Fig. 4 versus c_{gl} , the volume fraction of the E-glass (continuous curve). We observe that the branch corresponding to the micro-buckling mode lies below the macro-buckling branch only

for $c_{gl} < 0.3$. Also shown in Fig 3 is the well-known beam theory based criterion of Rosen [2] (long-dash curve). We note that this estimate, which was recently rederived in [8] by order of magnitude analysis, lies above the proposed criterion.

We emphasize that, within the obvious limitations of the proposed two dimensional buckling criterion, analogous estimates for E-glass/epoxy fiber-reinforced composites could be readily determined by following the same procedure followed above. The only difference would have been that the effective properties to be used in Eqns. 3 and 5 are those appropriate for unidirectional fiber composites (see, for example, [10]).

Finally, we note that the distinction between these two buckling modes is in agreement with analogous results obtained by Geymonat *et al.* [6] in their extensive and rigorous study of microscopic and macroscopic stability mechanisms. (See also [9] for corresponding results in the incompressible limit.) These investigators found that, usually, the microscopic buckling mode is the dominant failure mode in composites with a dilute concentration of the stiffer constituent, and that for larger volume fractions the buckling mode is a macroscopic one. In particular, it is interesting to note that by expressing the buckling criterion proposed in this work in terms of the critical stretches (instead of critical stresses) as functions of the volume fraction of the stiffer constituent, results that are reminiscent of those presented by these investigators are obtained (see, for example, Fig. 6.6 of [6] and Figs. 3 and 6 of [9]).

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A criterion for the onset of surface instabilities in reinforced solids is proposed. It is based on the combination of rigorous results for macroscopic and microscopic buckling modes. The macroscopic buckling stress is determined by solving a cubic equation which is expressed in terms of the effective elastic moduli of the composite. To determine a rigorous estimate for the microscopic buckling criterion numerical computations are required, however, it is demonstrated that the corresponding buckling strain depends, primarily, on two variables only. Accordingly, accurate estimates for the microscopic buckling strains may be interpolated from the numerical values provided in Table 1. Representative results are shown for an E-glass/epoxy laminated composite, demonstrating the role of the two modes. It is demonstrated that the new criterion is tighter than the well-known buckling criterion of Rosen [2], and agrees with corresponding findings of other investigators.

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